

Predictive Medicine

Personalised Medicine uses advances in biomedicine and information technology
Abridged version of the TA-SWISS study «Personalisierte Medizin»

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Personalised Medicine in brief

Rather than use standardised patterns of treatment to combat a disease, Personalised Medicine offers therapies which make allowances for peoples' particular physical characteristics; because not every medicine works the same way in all patients. Personalised Medicine thus holds out the prospect of more patients receiving treatments that work well and are free of serious side effects. The prerequisite for Personalised Medicine is for a large volume of data on biomarkers – i.e. on measurable biological physical characteristics – to be collected and analysed by computer. Personalised Medicine therefore builds on both new findings in biomedicine and on advances in information technology.

Personalised Medicine is already being used today to treat certain diseases. However, it remains to be seen whether the vision of comprehensive Personalised Medicine will ever become reality; in any event it is initially being developed as an element of advanced medicine.

Its opportunities ...

Because Personalised Medicine observes the biological characteristics of individual people, it can treat patients effectively and gently. For some patients, who have up to now received very little help, it holds out the prospect of suitable therapies possibly being found for them in the future. Personalised Medicine also enables people to be more proactive than before in their own health.

Personalised Medicine combines and analyses large volumes of health data. It thus reveals patterns which improve knowledge about many disease processes and accelerate medical progress.

If Personalised Medicine succeeds in realising its potential and making medical treatments simultaneously

more effective and more gentle, it could reduce the costs of healthcare. What we know about the human genome is constantly increasing, and hence also the possibilities of detecting predispositions to disease early on. Consequently, Personalised Medicine raises the importance of preventative measures that are in many cases less expensive than treating people who are already ill.

... its risks ...

Personalised Medicine can only bring its strengths to bear if it links biological characteristics with each other. This brings it rapidly into conflict with data protection, because it takes the combination of relatively few details to unequivocally identify a person – even if the data have been anonymised. Health data are particularly sensitive, and misuse can have serious consequences for the people concerned. If, for example, an employer learns that there is a high probability of one of its employees falling ill with cancer between the ages of forty and sixty.

Finally, Personalised Medicine assumes a great deal of specialised knowledge. Thus, for instance, the task of correctly interpreting the result of a gene test demands too much, not only of the patients involved but also many physicians. Personalised Medicine could therefore ultimately leave a lot of resigned and dissatisfied people in its wake – if insufficient attention is paid to information, counselling and additional training.

... and the most important recommendations

Genetic data enjoys special protection under the law. These high standards of protection should also be extended to data on non-genetic biological characteristics, because in future, as well as genetic information,

other data such as on proteins will increasingly allow statements to be made on disease risks.

Personalised Medicine places considerable demands both on attending physicians and on patients. Specialised knowledge is required, and it is essential to draw the right conclusions from complex situations and thus in many cases also to interpret statistical statements correctly. The continued development of Personalised Medicine therefore creates a need for training and additional training for medical personnel and increases the patients' need for counselling.

Worldwide, great importance is being attached to research into Personalised Medicine. In Switzerland, a scientific programme that deals specifically with the new findings on Personalised Medicine and enables researchers to network better with each other would be most welcome.

The study «Personalised Medicine» by TA-SWISS was conducted by an interdisciplinary team led by Anne Eckhardt (managing director of risicare GmbH, www.risicare.ch). The text boxes interspersed in the text quote from electronic self-help forums and illustrate how the internet is used by those affected to exchange views with and gather information from fellow sufferers.

Already ill, or still healthy?

If someone is in pain and feels ill, they seek medical treatment; the physician then sees it as her job to cure the disease. In the future, Personalised Medicine will help to recognise a predisposition to a particular condition even at this stage. It will thus prepare the way for a form of medicine that no longer treats only diseases but also guarantees better health. The boundary between healthy and ill is becoming blurred.

The report made the headlines in both the tabloid press and the serious media: Angelina Jolie, to many people the epitome of femininity, underwent an operation in May 2013 to have both breasts removed. The star had been led to take this step by a hereditary predisposition to breast cancer. Like her mother, who died from cancer at an early age, she carries a mutation in a gene called BRCA1. Her physicians calculated that there was an almost 90 per cent probability that she might also develop a breast carcinoma. The actress decided to pre-empt the disease by amputation.

Most people who visit a physician today are suffering from health problems. The patient explains that she has been suffering from headaches for days. The physician draws up a more precise picture of the situation and asks: where do the pains occur, what do they feel like, when are they noticeable? She assembles the medical history and asks about personal circumstances that could contribute to the disease. Does the patient have a job which might explain the headaches? Does she have too little sleep? Is she stressed? Biomedical tests such as a blood test complete the picture. The overall picture enables the physician to make a diagnosis. Depending on the disease, she then prescribes a suitable medication or arranges a course of physiotherapy treatment. The data collected are therefore used to detect varia-

tions from the norm. Only as many data as necessary are collected – including on grounds of cost.

That may possibly change very soon, because modern technical possibilities enable an almost unlimited amount of data to be collected, analysed and recorded. This could profoundly change the entire healthcare system. When the experts talk about Personalised Medicine they mean a form of medicine that builds on data relating to peoples' genetic make-up and takes the patient's individual blueprint into account. To this are added data about distinctive features of the metabolism

and other so-called biomarkers which can also be to do with a person's lifestyle.

Focus on the group, not the individual person

Although Personalised Medicine is based on individual data, it is not a «made-to-measure» medicine in the strict sense. It rather divides people up according to their specific biological characteristics into groups which are defined as precisely as possible. Certain cancers in particular are already treated using this principle: in the treatment of malignant skin cancer,

the University Hospital Zürich usually seeks to clarify whether a patient is the carrier of certain mutations which are sometimes mutually exclusive. Depending on which mutation is present, other active agents are used to combat the melanoma. With Personalised Medicine treatments are available for the first time which significantly improve the prognosis for patients with advanced melanoma. The current trend is very dynamic, so that further highly promising options are continually becoming available.

However promising the new approach is from the patients' point of view, it conflicts to a certain extent with processes in the healthcare system. At present, this is targeted at the standardised treatment of all patients who are suffering from a particular disease: case-based flat rates which are used in clinics to calculate costs (the so-called DRG – Diagnose Related Groups), assume that a disease follows a typical course and that a set plan has been determined to treat it. This system is not geared to reimbursing medical services that are matched to the characteristics of specific patient groups.

Optimise health – for life

In future, therefore, it is possible that the specialist in Personalised Medicine will determine which medication is most effective for the patient with chronic headaches and in what dose it should be prescribed. The example of Angelina Jolie points to a further development: Personalised Medicine not only diagnoses diseases, it is also able increasingly to identify disease risks. It will therefore be possible to offer (still) healthy people preventative treatment.

The predictive medicine raises questions that affect every individual: What do I want to know about my

risks of disease, and what do I not want to know? How well will I be able to deal with such information? When does a risk justify me talking preventative measures? If as a 50- to 60-year-old I have a 40 percent probability of falling ill with stomach cancer, should I start to follow a diet and take medication that promises to reduce the risk as a 25-year-old? And will my health insurance pay for this medication, or will I have to fund it myself?

New questions for society

Various studies suggest that people cope fairly well when they learn that the risk of a disease is slumbering in their genes – provided that they are counselled competently. However, our conception of disease and health is still affected by the new possibilities for prediction. Even today, there is often little to distinguish clearly between who is ill and who is healthy, and in future these boundaries will become even more blurred. Society therefore also sees itself confronted with new questions: what preventative measures should be funded by statutory health insurance? Will a person in future lose the right to support from a community of solidarity if he could take preventative measures for his health but does not?

Because Personalised Medicine distinguishes between patient groups which each have different biomedical characteristics, there will have to be a discussion about new procedures for clinical studies and the licensing of medicines. Classification into patient groups will in many cases lead to people being faced with clearly differing chances of effective prevention or treatment – depending on which biological characteristics they present. Questions about fairness and solidarity call for further careful analysis in connection with Personalised Medicine.

«We're always reading about associated diseases, or diseases that often occur alongside psoriasis. What's it like for you – which of the diseases that are typically linked to psoriasis do you have? In this survey you can tick a number of answers.» (Claudia, on the Psoriasis-Netz, uploaded on 20 October 2013, 14:33).

«It's just crazy how many people suffer from high blood pressure and obesity. I got both before the psoriasis. But the raised blood pressure started just before. The beta-blockers I was prescribed was probably one of the triggers of the psoriasis, as well as huge stress.» (Nüsschen, on the Psoriasis-Netz, uploaded on 20 October 2013, 18:41).

Psoriasis is a complex disease, and there may be mutations on over 40 genes involved at its onset; today, impending psoriasis can be identified early on by genetic testing. At the same time, the skin disease often is often accompanied by other less obvious complaints, and thus serves as a warning signal, for threatening hypertension and cardiovascular diseases, for instance.

Body patterns and habitual actions

Findings and measured data at the different levels on which the body is organised are a key basis of Personalised Medicine. In recent years, considerable progress has been made in this area. For the future, there are signs of a new understanding of medicine, in which the focus is on characteristic patterns of a person's biological features, rather than on individual diseases.

Can we personally influence our genetic information? For a long time this idea seemed absurd. In the last few years that has changed. Now, epigenetics is concerned with characteristics that can certainly be inherited but are not fixed in the actual DNA sequence. It has thus become clear that environmental factors affect epigenetics. Fitness training, for example, impacts on a number of genes that are linked to diabetes, and reduces the risk of disease. These changes are short-lived. Others persist over decades. Hence people whose mothers were affected by famine when they were pregnant still showed signs of epigenetic changes 60 years later.

«-omics» and biomarkers

Findings and measured data at the different levels («-omics») on which the body is organised are a key basis of Personalised Medicine. While genomics analogously describes the blueprint of an organism, transcriptomics corresponds to the construction manual and proteomics compares with the assembled cellular mechanism, metabolomics shows what is currently happening to the metabolism.

Genetic screening is an instrument of Personalised Medicine, the cost of which has fallen dramatically in recent years. Nevertheless, non-genetic analysis is also very important. In this respect it is conceivable that it will very soon be possible to take regular measure-

ments of relevant biomarkers at the protein level in blood, saliva or urine. By thus identifying metabolites, harmful substances can be detected after taking medication, which can help to prevent side effects. Findings about the role of microorganisms which colonise the human body (microbiomics) are also increasingly influencing Personalised Medicine.

The broad spectrum of biomarkers

In the interpretation of «-omics» data, medicine today is often close to its limits, because it is still unclear how an observation should be classified. Further research is needed here. Methods are being tested which will enable the interaction of different molecular biomarkers to be recorded and assessed. Biomarkers which enable definite statements to be made can be integrated into treatments with Personalised Medicine. But biomarkers with a minor effect are also medically significant because as a whole they can indicate weaknesses and strengths of the personal health profile.

The spectrum of non-molecular biomarkers covers a multitude of different measured values such as Body Mass Index, bone density or classification with the Clock Drawing Test which suspected dementia patients undergo. In many illnesses, family history is much more significant than any genetic screening.

It is not only data from the patient file that are important

It is not only the treating physician and the clinical researcher who are assigned an active role in Personalised Medicine. Every one of us can become a supplier of medically relevant information. At a time when many people are constantly swapping experiences on the internet with like-minded people, data about sports train-

ing sessions and personal fitness indicators are also being uploaded, compared and discussed. In this case, small sensors are used which can be attached to the body and feed data into the computer or Smartphone.

«Self tracking» is continuous self-observation, and «Quantified self» is the name given to the best known of these exercises. For some it is the play instinct and curiosity which encourages them to keep a record of their own lifestyle. Others use it to try to track down the causes for their migraines or other ailments. People who advocate comprehensive personalisation of medicine suggest that what was conceived as a tool for optimising one's own lifestyle could also be useful for medical science and clinical research. However, critics of permanent self-monitoring contend that the constant navel gazing at one's own sensitivities also ties down energies which would be better deployed elsewhere.

Focus on prevention

As knowledge grows about the different levels which the human body is organised on, and the potential for bioinformatic modelling of even complex biological systems and for considering the effects of the individual lifestyle, the analytical focus of medicine is shifting more strongly from molecular characteristics to the system characteristics of the human organism. A new understanding of medicine is emerging, in which the focus is on characteristic patterns of a person's biological characteristics, and no longer on individual diseases. When it becomes clear which of a patient's molecular mechanisms must be strengthened or modified, medicine is increasingly directed at maintaining health.

The person reflected in their data

Information technology is driving Personalised Medicine: Today, extensive genetic testing no longer matters much financially, and storage and computing capacities allow enormous volumes of data to be kept and processed. On the one hand, this opens up opportunities to understand health and disease better – on the other hand it is apparent that there are risks to data protection.

PatientsLikeMe is an internet platform that makes it possible to join networks for certain diseases in virtual communities and to call up healthcare services. For example, the electronic aids mentioned in the previous section can be used to follow and interpret the course of one's own disease. The company sells the data thus collected to interested parties, such as the pharmaceutical industry.

The electronic patient record as a prerequisite

Within the framework of Personalised Medicine large volumes of health data are collected, for example from genetic tests or examinations using imaging techniques. The electronic patient record is a key basis for using these data. The electronic patient record is a central element of the strategy of eHealth Switzerland. In future, the Federal Law on the electronic patient record will regulate the preconditions for processing data from the electronic patient record and help in enabling networked electronic healthcare services to be set up. For Personalised Medicine it is essential for attending physicians to be able to access all relevant data on a patient in the electronic patient record. Decision support systems can help here to interpret the abundance of data. In this area, however, there is still a need for research and development.

The abundance of data collected should in future be used for the further development of Personalised Medicine. It is expected that the large volumes of data will reveal previously unknown patterns and connections. Thus, for example, common causes might be identified for different clinical pictures, and more effective treatments developed on this basis. That is only possible, however, if data from many patients are recorded comprehensively and as far as possible in accordance with uniform standards. Substantial efforts are still needed to find appropriate technical solutions.

«Grass roots research»

The internet and social networks generally play an important role in connection with healthcare themes – and also in Personalised Medicine. Internationally, a number of providers have been established to collect, analyse and exchange personal health data. Users of PatientsLikeMe, for example, make their own health data available for research. These data are assessed by companies, universities and other interested parties, which have purchased the data in anonymised form

from PatientsLikeMe. Occasionally, however, they are also analysed at PatientsLikeMe itself. One study which became well known was on the effectiveness of lithium on lateral sclerosis, a disease that is often associated with damage to the nervous system. This study managed to achieve the same results as a subsequent scientific investigation – but much more quickly and more cheaply. In 2011 the journal Nature Biotechnology published the results of this study, which to some extent was organised in the manner of political «grass roots movements» from the basis of the people affected.

Studies that are based on such collections of data can indicate highly promising fields of research that should be well and truly spotlighted by the latest methods. In general, data and information that are collected and interpreted personally by those concerned will be important in Personalised Medicine. An essential precondition is that the vested interests of platforms and aids which are available on the internet should be made transparent in order to prevent crises of confidence.

Technical hurdles and challenges for data protection

Grouping data together in different formats and from different sources poses major technical challenges. There is also the fact that the more detailed and specific the grouped data, the more difficult it becomes to anonymise the information: it takes between 30 and 80 independent DNA characteristics to identify an individual with a high degree of probability. Correspondingly great are the challenges for data protection. Even if the individual data have been collected anonymously, the pooling of all the details enables conclusions to be made about the individual – possibly without the persons concerned knowing anything about it.

Effective protection of data is all the more important when there is major interest in this personal information. Life and health insurance companies are reliant for their calculations on being able to estimate the state of health of their customers as precisely as possible, and employers also like to make sure that their employees are not restricted by any kind of infirmity. Then there are the providers of all kinds of services –

«I got breast cancer a year ago, a tumour with HER2 3+. I've had 12 chemo sessions and radiotherapy and am now having hormone therapy with Nolvadex and Zoladex. It's not exactly the most pleasant therapy but I just get on with it. Now my oncologist finds out that an annual course of Herceptin would be good for reducing the risk of another relapse. Does anyone else have this type of tumour, and could anyone maybe help me a bit more? Love, Schmetterling» (in the Forum Krebs-Kompass.org, uploaded on 9 November 2005, 19:22).

«Hallo Schmetterling, Herceptin is recommended for HER2neu3+ and is used with great success, and it doesn't involve very many side effects either. Because these tumours are regarded as aggressive, if I were you I would accept this offer. What surprises me is the fact that you're getting Tamoxifen with HER2neu3+. It is strongly suspected that with HER2neu over expression is counterproductive. (...) Best wishes, TP» (in the Forum Krebs-Kompass.org, uploaded on 9 November 2005, 20:03).

from spa hotels for holidays and manufacturers of lifts for people with impaired mobility to producers of anti-allergenic foods. All of them are happy to make use of health data to promote their products in as target-oriented a way as possible. Data protection could therefore become crucially important when it comes to gaining the confidence of the general public on Personalised Medicine.

«Hallo Schmetterling, :wink: The risk of a relapse with HER2 positive tumours is actually considerably higher and the cancer cells are more aggressive, too. (...) I don't want to worry you saying that, but to encourage you to take Herceptin! (...) As for the AHT, you could certainly, as TP writes, change over to a aromatase inhibitor. I get Zoladex and Arimidex. Now I finally also understand why I don't get Tamox, thanks, TP, I didn't know that it's counterproductive! Best wishes and good night, :sleeping: Mice» (in Krebs-Kompass.org, uploaded on 9 November 2005, 22:48).

With various types of cancer, genetic analyses give an indication as to whether a therapy is working or not. So in the case of breast cancer, a growth factor receptor, the so-called HER2, can be present on the cancer cells. Herceptin is the name of an immunologically active protein – an antibody – against this receptor; it prevents the growth factors docking and thus inhibits the growth of the breast cancer cells. Many of those affected gain information and encouragement from the discussion in electronic self-help forums. The Tamoxifen that TP referred to is contained in the drug Nolvadex, which Schmetterling was prescribed; the abbreviation AHT stands for anti-hormone therapy.

Nothing to know by right

The Federal Act on Research involving Human Beings (Human Research Act, HRA) and the Federal Act on Human Genetic Testing (HGTA) set out the guidelines which point the way forward for Personalised Medicine. Allowance also has to be made for laws which are generally authoritative for health-care issues. In spite of the legal basis, physicians can find themselves faced with a moral dilemma when dealing with genetic testing.

The physician is bound by rules of professional confidentiality. This is enshrined in Articles 320 and 321 of the Swiss Penal Code, and it could be the most widely known rule which governs meetings between medical practitioners and patients. Also in effect since 1 January 2014 is section 321 a, which extends the scope of medical secrecy to findings made by research on human beings.

How much does one have to know ...

Despite very detailed regulations, Personalised Medicine raises some awkward questions. Genetic testing may possibly reveal unexpected results that will in the future perhaps lead to the onset of a disease which the person concerned may possibly not wish to know anything. In such a case, are physicians obliged to burden the patient with this surprising information? As the law stands, the case is clear: the affected person's right to self-determination also includes the right not to know. If someone does not wish to be told about unexpected findings, a physician may not disclose them even if he could also suggest effective measures to prevent the predicted illness. However, the Federal Act on Human Genetic Testing (HGTA) also mentions one exception: the physician is bound to provide information about a test result straight away if as a result an immediate threat endangering the life of the patient can be averted.

To make things worse, genetic information often affects not just the person being examined, but also their blood relations. Parents who have genetic tests carried out on their children without any medical grounds are thus interfering in the right of those children to decide for themselves in the future about what they want to know about themselves.

The situation becomes even more sensitive if someone posts the results of their gene test on the internet, for example by disclosing them in a sufferers' forum. Their blood relations are then threatened with losing control over who is allowed to access this information. Some legal experts are therefore speaking out in favour of a publication and/or disclosure ban on personal genetic data.

... and what does one have to test?

There is no obligation to subject oneself to genetic testing. The Act only permits genetic testing on medical grounds, to gain more information about a disease or any predispositions to disease. In concrete terms, this means that gene tests are only legal as part of a therapy, an occupational health check, or for declarations prior to taking out health or life insurance.

Presymptomatic gene tests are only permitted within a narrower medical context, i.e. during treatment by a physician or to clarify a potentially imminent threat of disease risks. With regard to occupational health checks or concluding insurance contracts, however, they are in principle prohibited, or require the express consent of the persons concerned. Nevertheless, limits are imposed on voluntariness. If, for instance, an occupational health check is stipulated for a job, in fact it amounts to a prohibition of employment if the job applicant refuses a test.

Some of the conflicts that can arise today when dealing with genetic testing stem from the fact that research is sometimes regulated by different laws than medical treatment. Something else that stands in the way of a consistent approach to the results of gene analyses is that genetic information enjoys special protection under the HGTA, by contrast with non-genetic biomarkers. Appropriate revisions to the Act could help to resolve this.

Nor can it be ruled out that Personalised Medicine will raise expectations in society that the individual will have to take more responsibility for his health. This could increase pressure on sick people, because they would no longer be perceived as victims needing help but as offenders who have indulged in a lifestyle which was incompatible with their predispositions. Personalised Medicine is ideal for patients who want to be heavily involved in their treatment and are striving for as much independence as possible; but if the right to self-determination is upheld, it must also be granted to people who feel no need to be involved.

The current system of health insurance is committed to the concept of solidarity: people who are blessed with good health are also paying for those who are plagued by chronic illnesses, and the insurance mandate ensures that no-one is excluded from the basic benefits. This principle is not called into question by Personalised Medicine – provided people retain sovereignty over their data. In future, it could still be necessary to discuss which solidarity society is prepared to support.

«29 March 2010, 12:30: Appointment with Prof. Moskopp and a stroke of luck in the gene lotto: (...) I'm hypermethylated. The crucial marker, whether the body is likely to respond to Temodal. (...) The probability was 45%. The implication is a couple of weeks or months. Statistically. But statistically it's also the case that after two years the curves go flat.» (Wolfgang Herrndorf, in the blog «Arbeit und Struktur»).

Genes which favour the development of cancer frequently display anomalies with methylation, i.e. with the biochemical «markings» of the DNA, which influence how the genes control the metabolism. With certain glioblastomas, for instance, methylation switches off a repair mechanism in the brain tumour which promises greater effectiveness of the cell growth inhibitor Temodal. The author Wolfgang Herrndorf recorded the story of his disease from the diagnosis of a brain tumour in his blog «Arbeit und Struktur». In August 2013 he took his own life; his blog has now appeared in a print edition from the Rowohlt-Verlag.

Shaping Personalised Medicine

Personalised Medicine dovetails with current efforts to introduce the electronic patient record in Switzerland. To ensure that the plethora of data produces beneficial findings, it is essential to take appropriate precautions. Data protection must protect health data from misuse and physicians need training that will equip them to handle complex medical situations and qualify them to give genetic counselling.

Personalised Medicine makes it possible to estimate predisposition to certain diseases even before they occur. Such forward-looking data are particularly sensitive, because if they get into the wrong hands the personal rights of the people concerned will be radically infringed.

Protect not just genotype data

Under the HGTA, special protection standards only currently exist for genetic data. The fact that less attention is given to all other biological characteristics is unjustifiable, because they also enable conclusions to be made about future risks of disease. Uniformly stringent standards should therefore be introduced for all biomarkers, and the scope of the HGTA should be extended to biological data that is not fixed in the genotype.

Prevent discrimination

Various laws prohibit discriminating against someone and excluding them from certain offers because of an inherited predisposition. Handling non-genetic health data which allows statements to be made about risks of disease and the threat of disabilities is not regulated by law. There must be clarification from politicians about whether a general ban on discrimination because of risks of disease should be approved.

Preserve personal rights

If people are confronted with details of imminent risks of disease against their wishes, this can substantially reduce their quality of life. However, it might be possible, thanks to accidental findings from genetic analyses to avert an imminent disease, or at least to combat it effectively. There should therefore be an obligation to pose questions enshrined in the law in order to clarify

whether a person who does not wish to be told about the accidental finding insists on her right not to know even if she could benefit from effective preventative measures.

The processing of anonymised data is not covered by the Data Protection Act, so there is no legal requirement to obtain the consent of the persons concerned to use anonymised data. Specific regulations for health

data should close this sensitive loophole. With regard to genetic data, the data protection interests of blood relatives of people tested should also be taken into consideration.

Qualify medical personnel and inform the public

Personalised Medicine increases the need for medical counselling. Current training of prospective physicians, however, does not adequately equip them for the requirements of Personalised Medicine. It is therefore essential to develop appropriate training and further training programmes and if need be to introduce a certificate of competence for medical practitioners who have achieved the appropriate qualifications.

The internet plays an increasingly major role in the storage and transmission of health data. In particular, if in future information about fitness and lifestyle should be placed in the health record, even if it is personally collected by the user, in-depth information is essential. Media education in schools should therefore look at the special importance of health data.

Research and development

The «eHealth Strategy for Switzerland», adopted by the Swiss Federal Council in 2007 provides for the introduction of the electronic patient record nationally. The objective is to network actors within the healthcare system in order to increase efficiency and to improve the quality and effectiveness of medical treatments. When designing the electronic patient record, it is important to ensure that it is also able to record findings of Personalised Medicine.

At international level, research on Personalised Medicine is considered to be very important – by contrast

with Switzerland, which does not have any scientific programme that is specifically concerned with Personalised Medicine, and where initiatives for a national biobank for storing biological materials and data have come to nothing. The Swiss National Science Foundation should therefore create a main area for research on Personalised Medicine and thus also promote co-operation with international research groups. There must also be some discussion about whether efforts to set up a national biobank should be intensified.

Do not lose sight of costs

Personalised Medicine requires substantial investment – even just to introduce the necessary technical standards and instruments, and to reinforce data protection. It seems plausible that these funds will be paid out one day, but this cannot be substantiated. In order to organise the framework conditions in such a way that the implementation of Personalised Medicine will be optimised, it is important to constantly evaluate its benefits. Some of the tools needed for this are lacking, making it essential to develop the appropriate methodological instruments.

Personalised Medicine could, especially as a result of statements on imminent disease risks, undermine the boundary between ill and healthy – a development that could, for example, have consequences for the reimbursement of medical examinations by the health funds. The Federal Office of Public Health should, at an early stage, deal with the shifts in the boundary area between «healthy» and «ill», in order to identify trends, to clarify the appropriate need for political action and to stimulate public debate on the subject.

«My Dad has been taking Tarceva for over a year now. He's 53 years old, has never smoked and has a spinal metastasis. This was 'killed' by irradiation and the tumour in his lung transformed into scar tissue thanks to Tarceva. (...) He's grown fairly stiff curly hairs. And his eyelashes and eyebrows feel like wire. And the skin problems too. We don't get rid of those completely with the creams, but just keep them under control. And he's not bothered about the spots and redness either – that's mainly a good sign, that it's working.» (LSN, in the Forum krebs-kompass.de, uploaded on 17 July 2013).

The drug Tarceva is a so-called EGFR inhibitor; the abbreviation stands for Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor. The active ingredient is therefore aimed at preventing cell growth, and thus also the growth of the cancer. An interesting clinical biomarker which indicates if the drug is working occurs in the form of an acne-like skin rash.

Study «Personalized Medicine»

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